

LEGAL SUPPORT OF HIGHER EDUCATION DIGITALIZING: CURRENT CHALLENGES

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Abstract: *Dependency on technologies is one of current tendencies. Digitalization development and spreading call for immediate reaction from the civil society, its recognition as one of the main challenges to education, higher education included. To foster its introduction, one needs new theoretical and practical decisions that delineate principles, and regularities in digital technologies development and affect the efficiency of law enforcement under the conditions of digital transformation of the world.*

Digitalization is a priority area in ensuring a country's competitiveness in the present globalized world. The modernizing of higher education will enable forming a qualitatively new system for human capital actuation and people's gaining digital competencies in accordance with rapid changes in economy, technologies, and labor markets.

Keywords: *Digital transformation; Digitalization; Education; Higher education*

1. Introduction

Education is a strategic resource for improvement of people's well-being, securing national interests, and authority of a state in the international arena. Raising the society's education level favors the introduction of modern information and production technologies, which in its turn determines economic development. Therefore, the Law "On National Security Foundations of Ukraine" in Article 8 relates preservation and strengthening the country's labor resource potential to the principal issues in state policies areas of Ukraine in social and humanitarian areas. In this aspect, a topical problem is that of forming a new qualitative labor capital – highly qualified workers adapted to the present labor conditions and capable of making efficient changes in future (Yushko A.M., 2017; Yushko A.M., 2020).

In current circumstances of the socio-economic development of Ukraine, the conditions of higher education functioning change drastically. The state and society's requirements to education quality are being raised, training technologies are fundamentally renovated, organizational and economic conditions of higher education institutions' operation change rapidly, and competition in the education services market is getting more acute. Reacting to the environment's dynamics and obeying the inherent need in perfection, higher education institutions (HEI) should accomplish their social mission through assistance in carrying out innovative activity, which should be targeted at considerable raise in quality of higher education, formation of new intellectual or knowledge-based education technologies, textbooks and training equipment, development of new financing sources for HEI, work motivations improvement, forming innovation infrastructure and supporting its operation (Klimova G.P., 2019).

The modern higher education development takes place within the context of global challenges, the most significant being a growing importance of knowledge society / knowledge-based economy; development of new trade agreements providing for, among other things, trade in education services; innovations in the information and

communication technologies; the growing role of market and the market economy, as stated in the UNESCO statutory document “Higher education in a globalized society”.

These principal global challenges are a catalyst to such new phenomena in the sphere of higher education as emergence of new education providers like multinational companies; corporation universities and media corporations; new forms of education support, including the distance, virtual, and direct education that are provided by private companies as well; a great diversification in qualifications and certificates on education; a great mobility of students, programs, providers, and projects that go beyond national borders; accentuation on life-long training which in its turn leads to a growth in demand for post-secondary education; a raise in the amounts of private investments in the service sector, namely its segment of higher education services (Klimova G.P., 2021).

2. MAIN MATERIAL EXPOSITION

The National Strategy for Education Development in Ukraine till 2021, approved by the edict of the President of Ukraine No 344 of June 25, 2013, accentuates that the most acute problems that impede the development of the new quality of education are: (1) insufficient correspondence of education services to requirements of society, and the labor market needs; (2) insufficient orienting of the structure and the contents of vocation-and-technical, higher, and postgraduate education to the labor market needs and current economic challenges; (3) unadjusted and quite inefficient employment system for higher education graduates, the system of their professional guidance.

The Concept of Ukrainian Education Development for 2015–2025 developed by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine accentuates on the need in systematic reform of education, which is to be an object of social consensus, the understanding of the fact that education is one of the main levers of civilizational advance and economic development (Yushko A.M., 2020).

3. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Corresponding to the present-day needs, a rapid growth in the amount of knowledge requires the introduction of new approaches to education organizing and search for innovative forms of passing and assimilation of knowledge and competencies. A rapid development of digital technologies stimulates creation and introduction of innovative forms of education capable of catching up with the changes. A person’s adjustability to changeable labor market becomes a crucial factor that puts forward the lifelong learning model by way of proliferating various courses in specific professions with the use of new methods and technologies of teaching like Online, Open & Flexible. The model includes the following subsystems: the informal and non-formal education (by the extent of institutionalizing); the distance education (by the mode of the training process organizing); online education (by the applied means of its implementation); the mixed system (the combination of traditional and online means of training) to ensure cognitive flexibility (Babayev V.M., Stadnyk I.V. & Momot T.V., 2019).

4. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to the data shared by The International Council for Open and Distance Education (ICDE), the UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning (UIL), and Study Portals (SP), the European educational market demonstrates similar tendencies. The data of the “Impact of Distance Education on Adult Learning” report reveal that only 20 % of the European higher education institutions that took part in the survey do not offer any distance courses, while 9 % offer obtaining exclusively online education. It should be noted that nearly all Scandinavian universities provide some form of distance education. Half of the European higher education institutions introduce online courses as an addition to the mainstream education process; another 20% build up their training on the basis of a mixed model (dual-model type), which gains ever more popularity.

In accordance with the Erasmus + Strategic Partnership Program (2017 – 2020) titled “Open Virtual Mobility: Accessible Opportunities for Virtual Mobility Skills in Higher Education”, work is underway on forming the European Virtual Mobility Learning Hub with the use of a number of innovational digital training means like Open Credentials (Open Badges, Blockcerts), the semantic Competency Directory, evidence-based E-Assessment, algorithm-based matching tool for collaborative learning groups, pedagogic methods like Open Learning by Design and Crowd Creation, and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs).

Therefore, the European Commission has concentrated quite actively on the issue of digital education. Presently, the Plan of Measures on Digital Education (2021–2027) has been drafted, which is aimed at fostering development of a highly efficient digital education environment. Among the areas of work determined in this document, there are development of ethical standards of the artificial intelligence (AI) applications, and the use of data on students and teachers obtained in the course of the training process. The amounts of data in the form of training materials, the awarded points, types of training and research work have considerably increased due to inaccessibility of the offline form of communication with pupils and students. A number of important issues have arisen concerning the

provision of access to lectures in real-time mode to a precisely specified number of people, their identification and establishing the person's actual presence at an event, not solely their technical connection to a class, etc. (Golovko O.M., 2020).

In connection with diversifying of the areas of higher education universities' activities, organizations that are engaged in analyzing the content of this process and changes occurring therein are formed and developed. The European leaders in this respect are the European Association of Higher Education (EAIE, the Netherlands), the Higher Education Internalization Center at the Catholic University of the Sacred Heart (CHEI, Italy), and the European Consortium for Accreditation (ECA). The development of the internalization process is enhanced, to a great extent, by various EU programs (for instance, ERASMUS, SOCRATES, TEMPUS), as well as projects initiated by national organizations of the Economic Cooperation and Development Organization member states (USAID, IREX, British Council, DAAD, CIDA, EduFrance, et al.), which are targeted at academic mobility development (Klimova G.P., 2019).

The digital skills and competencies are becoming a token of full-fledged development of digital economy, which determines the expediency and topicality of studying the digital transformations in the higher education area under conditions of Ukraine's European integration.

According to the outcomes of a research by the World Economic Forum, the top ten of the most needed competencies in 2020 would include: 1) combined problem-solving; 2) critical thinking; 3) creativity; 4) people management; 5) actions coordination with others; 6) emotive intellect; 7) forming judgements and decision making; 8) orienting at servicing; 9) interaction, negotiating.

The education activity subjects are physical persons or legal entities (a higher education institution, an enterprise, an office, an organization) that carry out education activity. A legal entity possesses the status of an education institution if its main kind of activity is education. The rights and duties of an education institution provisioned by this Law and other laws of Ukraine pertain also to a physical person-entrepreneur or a structural unit of a legal entity of private or public law whose main kind of activity is education. Education activity in Ukraine is licensed with taking into consideration the peculiarities stipulated by special laws in the area of education. The license conditions for carrying out education activities are approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine Decree of December 25, 2015 No 1187. That is, for carrying out education activities, obtaining a license is required (Fedosyuk Yu., 2020).

For activating the process of Ukraine's joining the European environment through accomplishment of purposeful acts in implementing state policies in the area of information and communication technologies, scientists and experts in the information technology sector have developed "the Digital Agenda of Ukraine 2020" (the digital strategy). The main goal of the document is implementation of the initiatives concerning the cooperation with the EU in the digital sector and building up the country's innovation infrastructure and digital transformations to stimulate the internal consumption markets, to introduce and manufacture digital technologies in the years to come. The Strategy determines the vision of transforming the present economy from the "analog" to its digital form, the measures concerning implementation of the corresponding stimuli for digitalization of socio-economic life, the challenges and instruments of the digital infrastructure development, gaining digital competencies by citizens; it also determines critical areas and projects of the country's digitalization (Babayev V.M., Stadnyk I.V. & Momot T.V., 2019).

Digital transformation or digitalization is a wholesome revision of a business model, transformation of all processes and transition to the use of modern instruments in banking, financial markets, trade, manufacturing, economy, professions, education, business, and society (Zhosan G., 2020). Digitalization is defined as a process of transforming physical data into digital format which ensures its protection, a longer storage period, fast access, etc.

Digitalization is understood as a neologism that entered the Ukrainian language only a few years ago, being transliteration of the corresponding English word, and which means, according to a dictionary definition, changes in all areas of social life connected with the use of digital technologies. This word is a simplified form of a more precise term of "digital transformation" and is a manifestation of the global "digital revolution". An unalienable component of digitalization in a modern state are the processes of transparency of any organization and of its operation.

The area of education undergoes irreversible changes. The prevailing trend nowadays is to gain additional education. The Bitkom Company, a German digital association, has conducted a research which revealed that three out of four respondents complain that they lack time at workplace to obtain additional knowledge. This is due to a rapid development in information technologies. Therefore, in such an epoch it is important to be constantly "prepared for learning". Furthermore, it is necessary to be able to join individual elements of information (Tatsyi V., Getman A. & Ivanov S. et al., 2010), to demonstrate creative approach to problem solving, and to respond rapidly to new requirements.

The main directions in education development are: speed – the training keeps up to date, for usual accumulation of knowledge is no longer relevant; enthusiasm and motivation are the basic principles in education where teachers are becoming coordinators, guiding their students in the online and the offline mode; accessibility to materials in

real time which facilitates the process of obtaining new knowledge; the interdisciplinary content, which eliminates borders between production, business, and other areas, and therefore requires knowledge from different areas of life (Zhosan G., 2020).

Providing of all educational online services in a broad sense is, in essence, e-commerce relations. Legal relations in the e-commerce area at the time of commencing digital legal actions are regulated by the Law of Ukraine “On Digital Commerce”. That is, when performing educational online activities, the business entities are to observe the requirements of the mentioned law, particularly requirements concerning making an online agreement and in respect to the information, access to which is to be ensured (Fedosyuk Yu., 2020).

The distance education (DE) or the distance training (DT) is education focused on pedagogy and androgogy, technologies and training-and-methodology systems whose goal is delivering knowledge to students and pupils who are physically “out of place”. According to the US Education Department, “this is the process of providing and securing access to training for cases when the source of information and pupils are separated from one another by time and distance”. In other words, DT is a process of forming an education environment which best corresponds to pupils’ needs outside the classroom. Instead of attending the courses in person, teachers, pupils, and students can communicate from time to time at their own discretion, exchanging printed or digital mass media materials, or by means of technologies enabling them to communicate in real time and by other online instruments. The distance courses that for any reason require participants’ physical presence in situ, including carrying out examination sessions, are called hybrid or mixed training courses.

Online training can be viewed as an alternative to a personality training method or as an addition to it. Online training usually gives a student a wider choice, as well as responsibility for their own training.

Currently, there is a wide range of technological options for carrying out distance education. They can be subdivided into the basic categories that follow. Voice: training audio tools include interactive technologies of telephone connection, audio conferences, and short-wave radios. Passive (i.e. one-way) audio tools include tapes and radio. Video: instructive video tools include stationary images like slides, preliminary prepared moving images (for instance tape or a videocassette), and moving images in real time combined with audio conferences. Data: computers send and receive information in digital form. For this reason, the term “data” is used to describe this broad category of training tools. Computer programs for distance training are various and include the following aspects: Computer instruction (CI) uses a computer as a self-sufficient teaching machine, which enables conducting individual classes. Computer guided instruction (CGI) uses a computer for generating instructions and tracking students’ notes and progress. Computer-mediated learning (CML) describes computer programs that facilitate instructions presentation. Printing is a fundamental element of distance training programs and the basis on which all other systems of material presentation have formed. Various formats of printing are available, including textbooks, teaching aids, workbooks, course programs, and thematic research.

The types of available technologies that are applied in distance education can be subdivided into two groups: the synchronous and asynchronous. The synchronous technologies are the online mode of training, wherein all the participants are simultaneously “present” according to the timetable. Web-conferences are an example of a synchronous technology. Asynchronous technologies are a mode of online training wherein the participants get access to training materials by their individual timetable. Students are not obliged to be present simultaneously. Examples of asynchronous technologies are messaging forums, email, and recorded video.

Distance education provides at least three positive aspects, such as a wider access: DE can encompass insufficiently affluent pupils population who cannot attend school and offers those education services which these pupils would like to get; possibilities for new accomplishments: DE brings up the need in life-long training in community, in education, providing access to education to students who do not belong to the traditional age-group; adapting to new technologies and a new environment.

Education institutions can adopt distance education as a means of adapting to rapid changes in technologies applied nowadays in the training process.

5. Conclusion

Due to continuity of radical social changes related to the development and increased rates of growing knowledge together with information and communication technologies development, education activity cannot stand aside.

Reforming of higher education should meet the requirements of the needs in development of economy digitalization and society in general. It is one of the main tasks of a competitive country under globalization conditions, while digital technologies, in their turn, are to make the training process mobile, differentiated, and individual. In such conditions, one should primarily speak of modernizing the education system in the direction of ensuring conditions for the development of citizens’ digital skills.

Nevertheless, digitalization in Ukraine, unlike other countries, is just gaining momentum, notably rather slowly and separately from the academic education, which results in extremely low level of digital competency in all the existing segments of the state education system and does not meet the labor market needs.

References:

- “Digitalization – the word of 2019 in Ukraine according to the “Myslovo” online dictionary”. Retrieved from: <https://itc.ua/news/didzhitalizacziya-slovo2019-roku-v-ukra%D1%97ni-zaersi%D1%94yu-onlajn-slovnika-mislovo/>.
- “The National Strategy of Education Development in Ukraine till 2021”. Approved by the President of Ukraine Decree of 25.06.2013 vol. 344: The Official Bulletin of Ukraine, #50, Art. 1783, 2013.
- Babayev, V.M., Stadnyk, I.V., & Momot, T.V. (2019). “Digital transformation at higher school under globalization”. *Communal facilities in cities*, vol. 2, ed. 148, pp. 2-9.
- Distance education in European higher education. Report 1 (of 3). The IDEAL Project, 2014. Retrieved from: https://idealprojectblog.files.wordpress.com/2013/11/ideal_report_final.pdf
- Fedosyuk, Yu. (2020). “Present-day models of juridical online education, regulation aspects, and peculiarities in its tax regulating in Ukraine”. LIGA 360. PRL: https://buh.ligazakon.net/analytics/195491_osvtnya-onlajn-dyalnst-pravov-ta-podatkov-aspekti
- Golovko, O.M. (2020). “Digital education in the EU: the internet of things in action”. *Social and digital transformation: theoretic and practical problems of legal regulation*. Science and practical conference, Kyiv, December 10, 2020. Edited by Baranov O.A., Furashev V.M., Dorogyh S.O. Kyiv: Phoenix, p. 52.
- Klimova, G.P. (2019). “Conditions for innovations environment formation at higher school”. *The bulletin of “Yaroslav Mudriy Juridical Academy of Ukraine” National University*, series “Sociology”, vol. 4, pp. 44-52, 2019.
- Klimova, G.P. (2021). “Higher education internationalization under global challenges”. *The bulletin of “Yaroslav Mudriy Juridical Academy of Ukraine” National University*, series “Philosophy, philosophy of law, political studies, sociology”, vol. 1(48), pp. 185-205.
- Kuprina, K.A. (2016). “Digitalization: the notion, prerequisites, and the application areas”. The Scientific Conferences Bulletin. *Information services quality. The International science-and-practical conference*, Tambov, May 31, 2016, vol. 5-5 (9), pp. 259-262.
- Modern scientific innovations (part II). (2018). The International Conference of February 24-25, 2018, Kyiv: MCND, p.6.
- Tatsyi, V., Getman, A., Ivanov, S. [et al.] (2010). “Semantic network of knowledge in science of law”. Proceedings of the IASTED International Conference on Automation, Control, and Information Technology: *The International Association of Science and Technology for Development*, Anaheim, USA; Calgary, Canada, pp. 218–222.
- Yushko, A.M. (2017). “Improvement of legal forms of education institutions interaction with employers in young specialists training and employment as one of the areas in state socio-economic policies”. (A monograph). Legal and legislative support of economic security of Ukraine. Getman, A.P., Bilousov, Ye.M., Anisimova G.V. (eds.). Kharkiv: Pravo, Section 3, Subsection 3.2, 229-256.
- Yushko, A.M. (2020). “Higher juridical education in Ukraine: current challenges”. *Modern problems of the development of law and economics in an innovative society*: International conference, Velyko-Tyrnovo, Bulgaria, March 20, 2020, pp. 271-277.
- Zhosan, G. (2020). “The situation with digitalization development in Ukraine”. *Economic analysis*. Vol. 30(1), part 2, pp. 47-51.